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SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL TRANSLATION AND ITS TYPES

Musabekova Madina Narimanbekovna

Teacher of the Department of English Translation Theory

Uzbek State University of World Languages

E-mail: m.musabekova3103@gmail.com<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10648713>

Annotation: This article studies the classification of scientific and technical translation, depending on the method of processing the original material.

Key words: types of scientific and technical translation, full written translation, oral translation.

Currently, scientific and technical translation is considered as a special type of translation activity and a special theory that explores this type of activity. It is easy to guess that scientific and technical translation is the translation of special texts of a scientific and technical nature, carried out by specific methods that differ from the translation of fiction. The specificity of this translation lies in the fact that it deals with a special sphere of human activity - various fields of science and technology, for the expression of which there are certain lexical, grammatical and stylistic means of language.¹

All scientific and technical literature represents a certain functional style of speech, the characteristic features of which are its informativeness (content), logic (strict consistency, clear connection between the main idea and details), accuracy and objectivity and the clarity and intelligibility resulting from these features.²

The main goals of translating scientific and technical literature are that the translation product must meet the criteria of equivalence and adequacy. Adequate or equivalent translation is a translation that is carried out at a level necessary and sufficient to convey an unchanged plan of content while maintaining the corresponding plan of expression, i.e. norms of the translating language. Consequently, the translation of technical and scientific texts requires compliance with the features characteristic of the scientific and technical style of speech. The specificity of the translation of scientific and technical materials lies in the increased requirements for the accurate transmission of information

¹ Макеева М.Н. Технический перевод в повседневной жизни: учеб. пособие для студентов инженерно-технических специальностей / М.Н. Макеева, С.В. Начерная, О.В. Чуксина. - Тамбов. Изд-во Тамб. гос. техн. ун-та. 2004. - 250 с

² Ередина И.В. Перевод в научно-технической деятельности: учебное пособие. - Томск: Изд-во Томского политехнического университета, 2010. -121 с.

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contained in the original, including the correct transmission of special terms. However, this does not mean a literal translation of the text.

Also, one should not assume that any translator, even one who knows the original language perfectly, will translate a technical text reliably, and vice versa, that a good technical specialist who knows the original language, but is not a professional translator, will be able to qualitatively translate a scientific article from his own language into his native language. As we already know, from ordinary language translation, technical translation differs in specific terminology, which requires the translator to have knowledge in the field of the translation topic and free orientation in terms.³ Since the same terms in different fields of science and technology may have different meanings. You need to be a specialist in the field to which the text to be translated belongs, with appropriate education or a certain amount of work experience in your field in order to freely operate with special terminology. The translator must not only understand the text perfectly, but also accurately present it, as this is required by document standards; therefore, excellent command of both the language of the original text and the target language is necessary.

In addition to a number of lexical and grammatical features, there is another classification of scientific and technical translation, which depends on the method of processing the original material. These are two larger classes: complete written translation, which is also divided into abstract, annotative and “express information” translation, and oral translation, within which a consultative type of translation is distinguished. The main type of technical translation is full written translation. All scientific and technical information is processed only in this form (instructions, diagrams, declarations, payment orders and other scientific and technical documents). Work on a complete written translation includes a number of stages that have a certain order of execution. Failure to follow the sequence of steps may lead to a decrease in the quality of the translation.

- At the first stage, “acquaintance” with the original text occurs. The translator must find out the context in which to work and understand what is expressed in the original language.
- Then, at the second stage, the translator makes a rough translation of the text, trying to convey in his own words the information he has learned in Russian. The quality, uniformity and logic of presentation should be constantly monitored.

³ Казакова Т.А. Практические основы перевода. - СПб.: Перспектива. Изд-во «Союз», 2008. - 127 с.

- At the third stage, the final editing of the translated text takes place, eliminating inaccuracies, checking the style, quality, uniformity and logic of the text.
- The final stage is the translation of the title, which carries the essence of the text, so the titles are translated last, taking into account all the features of the original

The following types of technical translation that we will consider are abbreviated versions of full written translation. One such shortened version of full written translation is abstract translation. The translator is not required to perform a complete translation, but only to concisely convey the essence or main idea contained in the source text. This type also has a number of successive stages.

- The first stage is familiarization with the original, reviewing specialized literature to become familiar with this area and its terminology.
- The second stage is to highlight secondary parts and repetitions in the text using square brackets.
- The third stage is reading the highlighted passages to eliminate disproportions and incoherence.
- The fourth stage is the final one, here a complete written translation of the part of the original remaining outside the brackets is performed, which is a coherent text built according to the same logical plan as the original.
- If the original contains drawings, diagrams or drawings, then the translator selects the most important and detailed illustrations in the text, indicating their place in the original text.

However, abstract translation should not be confused with another type of technical translation, which is called abstract translation. These concepts are often considered interchangeable synonyms, since both of these translations ultimately represent condensed information compared to the original. However, brevity of presentation is the only characteristic that unites them.

Annotative translation is a type of translation that consists of compiling an annotation of the original in another language, that is, compiling a brief description of the content of the original text.

There are two types of abstracts that are very different from each other: the abstract of a special article or book and the abstract of a foreign patent. Consider first the abstract of a special article or book - this is a brief description of the original, which sets out its contents in the form of a list of main issues. This type of translation is carried out in the following sequence:

- the translator reads an article or book;

- formulates the main provisions of the original: lists its main issues or describes its structure and content.

The volume of an annotated translation compared to the original may vary, but usually does not exceed 500 printed characters.

The difference between annotative translation and other types of technical translation is that here the reproduction of a small part of the information contained in the original is carried out in the form of a description, and not in the form of an actual presentation. Abstract translation of patents is a type of translation that is used when compiling patent files. The translator's task is to briefly outline the essence of the invention, and not to characterize it. It is also necessary to reflect what is new that distinguishes this invention from similar ones. It is also not required to provide an idea of the structure of the invention and a critical assessment.

The second method of abstracting is “express information”, and translation of the “express information” type refers to types of written technical translation, which consists of compiling an abstract of a foreign scientific and technical article or patent in language without first abridged the original.

Stages of working with text:

- detailed study of the material;
- presenting the essence of the original text from the translator's point of view in its own way, which may not coincide with the plan of presentation of the original article.

The scope of this type of translation is determined by the translator himself or determined by the customer based on some technical considerations. The difference between an abstract translation and a translation of the “express information” type is that good “express information” on a patent should make it possible to make the invention, and not just get an idea about it.

However, there are often cases when technical interpretation is needed; as a rule, this is necessary for events with a large number of people: seminars, symposiums, expeditions, etc. Such translation can be carried out sequentially or synchronously

Another type of interpretation is advisory. This is a type of technical translation that includes oral annotations, oral abstracting, oral translation of headings, quotes, notes, and selective sight translation. Translators and consultants help specialists with poor command of a foreign language understand what is being said. A specialist can ask what is said in a particular article, and the consulting translator must make an annotation or abstract on the

material he has. However, in any case, careful consideration of the context is required.

Thus, we considered scientific and technical translation as a special type of translation activity. We studied the specifics of scientific and technical translation, which lies in the fact that it deals with a special sphere of human activity - various fields of science and technology, for the expression of which there are certain lexical, grammatical and stylistic means of language.

The quality of translation directly depends on the competence and professionalism of translators, whose education is a very important condition for its improvement.

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